

Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

LISA

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In early life, accurate description of structural changes in the developing human brain is crucial for understanding healthy development and identification of neurodevelopmental disorders. Existing adult brain deep learning (DL) based segmentation tools struggle with pediatric MRI due to poor gray/white matter differentiation and rapid growth. These challenges impair the ability of existing algorithms to accurately segment pediatric brain structures even with high field (1.5T or 3T) MRI systems. In low and middle-income countries, high field MRI systems are rare due to their high cost and maintenance required. To fill this gap, 0.064T Hyperfine SWOOP scanners are being tested in these settings by the UNITY Consortium, funded by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Despite lower image quality, low-field MRI offers portability, cost-effectiveness, and eliminates the need for sedation in children. To continue to translate recent improvements in infant brain segmentation to underprivileged communities, we resume with the Low-field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance (LISA) challenge. We expand the dataset of the first two tasks of the LISA challenge, first presented at MICCAI 2024. Task 1 involves evaluating objective, quantifiable quality assurance (QA) methods that rate the overall quality of low-field MRI to ensure the acquired MRI meets specific accuracy and consistency standards. Task 2 is centered around the automatic segmentation of subcortical structures such as the hippocampi which are pivotal subcortical structures linked to cognitive and memory functions, and often implicated in abnormal neurodevelopment and the basal ganglia, a group of subcortical nuclei critical for motor control, cognitive functions, and behavioral regulation, which are often implicated in disorders involving motor and executive dysfunction. The overarching goal of this challenge is to develop optimal and publicly available DL tools to assess and segment ultra-low field T2-weighted magnetic resonance images of the brain in early childhood.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

pediatric, MRI, low field, quality assurance, segmentation, hippocampus, MICCAI, brain, neurodevelopment, Africa, South Asia

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

To our knowledge, this is the first challenge of its kind to utilize low field pediatric magnetic resonance images.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

N/A

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

MICCAI 2024's LISA challenge supported 39 participants. After publicity and outreach during MICCAI 2024, we expect to receive at least as many participants this year as well.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

For our online challenge, we will use the Synapse platform. On-site we will not require any resources beyond those necessary for powerpoint presentations of the results e.g. - projector, screen, microphone

TASK 1: Quality assessment of low field neonatal MR images

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

During the initial stages of life the human brain undergoes rapid tissue growth and development after birth. Accurately capturing and describing structural changes from magnetic resonance images (MRI) during this vital period is crucial for gaining new perspectives on healthy brain development and enabling the early identification of neurodevelopmental disorders.

While validated brain automatic quality analysis tools exist for adult brains, efforts to directly translate existing adult brain algorithms to pediatric MRI have generally failed. This is partly due to the poor gray/white matter differentiation of the developing brain and its rapid growth throughout the first years of life. In low and middle income countries, high field MRI systems are rare due to the high cost and maintenance required. More accessible MRI systems like the 0.064 T Hyperfine scanner would help to assess gross anatomical abnormalities; structural delineation challenges are further compounded in these lower resolution imaging environments. Despite the loss in image quality and challenges with image analysis, there are great advantages of using low field MRI including portability at the point of care of patients, small clinical costs with usability in low resource settings and elimination of sedation for young children.

To address the quality challenges in lowfield MRI, we introduce the first task of the Lowfield pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and Quality Assurance (LISA) challenge, which focuses on the evaluation of objective quantifiable quality assurance QA methods. These methods will rate the overall quality of lowfield 0.064 T MRI and ensure that the acquired MRI meets specific accuracy and consistency standards in the provided data.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

pediatric, MRI, low field, quality assurance, MICCAI, brain, neurodevelopment, Africa, South Asia

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Lead Organizers: Natasha Lepore (1,4) , Marius George Linguraru (2,3), Sean Deoni(6,7). Other organizers: Jeffrey Tanedo(1), Rahimeh Rouhi(1), Austin Tapp(2), Marvin Nelson(5). Data Contributors : Victoria Nankabirwa(8)(9), Sean Deoni (6,7), Kirsty Donald (10), Sadia Parkar (11), Sidra Kaleem (11), Salman Osmani (11)

1 CIBORG Laboratory, Department of Radiology, Children's Hospital Los Angeles; 2 Sheikh Zayed Institute for Pediatric Surgical Innovation, Children's National Hospital; 3 Departments of Radiology and Pediatrics, George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences; 4 Department of Pediatrics and Biomedical Engineering, University of Southern California; 6 Advanced Baby Imaging Lab, Rhode Island Hospital; 7

Departments of Pediatrics and Diagnostic Radiology, Warren Alpert Medical School at Brown University; 8 Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda; 9 St. Francis Hospital - Nsambya, Kampala, Uganda ; 10 Department of Paediatrics and Child Health, University of Cape Town; 11 Aga Khan University Hospital

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Natasha Lepore - nlepore@chla.usc.edu
 Children's Hospital Los Angeles
 4650 Sunset Blvd, Los Angeles, CA, 90027, USA
 Department of Radiology and Imaging
 Phone: 323-361-2411

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

As with the LISA 2024 Challenge, we plan to use the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks; Synapse.org) for the challenge. This platform has been used for numerous other challenges, including the CBTN-CONNECT-DIPGr-ASNR-MICCAI Pediatric Brain Tumor Segmentation Challenge 2023, organized by Dr. Linguraru.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

synapse.org Synapse Project SynID is syn53282349. <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn55249552/wiki/626951>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Data used to train algorithms is not restricted to only the data provided by the challenge. Publicly available online and/or synthetic datasets are allowed. Our aim is to solve the segmentation and quality assurance of low-field MRI with the best possible tools. Investigator-owned data may be used only if data is made available to the community before August 8th, 2025, which is when the testing phase begins.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

First prize in each task will be awarded \$1000 each.

Second prize in each task will be awarded \$500 each.

Third prize in each task will be awarded \$250 each.

Top three teams in each task will receive award certificates.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods for each task will be announced publicly and these participants will be invited to present their method. All participant rankings (training, validation and testing) will also be made publicly available on the challenge website leaderboard. All participant methods that are ranked in the testing phase will have their accompanying short LNCS style paper (see next section) made visible to organizers and challenge participants. Making the participants' paper public will support methodological reproducibility and the open-source spirit the organizers seek to embody in this challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Authors participating in the evaluation of their containerized model against the unseen test data are required to submit a short 8- to 11- page LNCS style paper through the LISA CMT by Friday, July 25th at 11:59 PM Pacific Time. Papers will be reviewed for suitability for online distribution. If challenge organizers deem that the method is not reproducible via the short paper instructions, then the method will not be evaluated and thus not considered for ranking. In some cases, organizers may provide comments to improve the short paper within the deadline. Details on training time and resources required to reproduce a participant's submission will be required in the short paper. Challenge participants must abide by the guiding principles for responsible research use and data handling within the Synapse Commons Platform as described in the Synapse Governance documents and by the Challenge's Official Rules. Publication embargo: Challenge participants are permitted to publish individual challenge results restricted to their own submitted method and ranking. Overall Challenge results or analysis thereof is restricted until Challenge organizers and participants have jointly published (or pre-published) an overview paper on the results and best performing strategies. The challenge organizers intend to aggregate the

methods and summarize the results of LISA 2025 as a single journal manuscript with the goal of publication in journals of Medical Image Analysis, IEEE TMI, or a journal of similar impact factor. Participants will be contacted through Synapse-affiliated email addresses when this condition has been met. This information will also be posted within this Synapse project. Acknowledgement: Challenge participants and other data users are permitted to use, publish and present the Challenge results, after the embargo period, provided they acknowledge the LISA challenge organizing members as follows: "Data used in this publication were obtained as part of MICCAI 2025's Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance (LISA) Challenge through Synapse ID syn53282349", Publications using challenge resources will be required to cite the overview paper of LISA 2025 and acknowledge the support of the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, which provided funding used for supporting data collection, curation, and processing.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Validation and Training Phase csv files with QC predictions are to be submitted on the Synapse Platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn55249552/wiki/627686>

Test Phase submissions are done via MLCube containers submitted on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn55249552/wiki/627696>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

To permit participant's method fine tuning, we will release the validation set in June (see timetable below). Validation ground truth data will not be released, but scores based on predictions will be provided to participants. Participants can select their final test submissions based on these validation results. After the validation phase ends, participants are allowed a maximum of 2 final testing submissions for each task, or 4 total submissions. The best scoring method of each task (2 methods per team) will be selected for final ranking. Neither test images nor their ground truths will be made public.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Wednesday, 16 April 2025

Challenge launch

Registration opens

Wednesday, 30 April 2025

Release of training data with ground truth labels

Tuesday, 17 June 2025

Release of validation data (without labels)

Tuesday, 24 June 2025

Validation phase opens

Friday, 25 July 2025

Validation phase ends (submission deadline of segmentation files)

Submission deadline of short papers in CMT, reporting method and preliminary results.

Saturday, 26 July 2025

Testing phase opens

(available only to participants who submitted short papers)

Saturday, 9 August 2025

Testing phase ends (submission deadline of MLCubes)

Saturday, 9 August – Friday, 29 August 2025

Evaluation of MLCubes on testing data

(performed by challenge organizers)

Monday, 1 September 2025

Top performing methods contacted for preparing oral presentation slides

Tuesday–Saturday, 23–27 September 2025

Presentation of Challenge, Announcement of the final top 3 ranked teams

Late October 2025

Camera-ready submission of extended papers for inclusion in the associated workshop proceedings

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The low-high field magnetic resonance image data that will be used for the training, validation, and testing of algorithms was acquired through the UNITY project funded by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) at multiple international sites. Ethics approval was obtained at each site following the local standards and all data were fully de-identified before inclusion in the project. The protocol for releasing the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data contributing institution and data inclusion in the LISA challenge was approved by the BMGF. Training and validation data will be made available to challenge participants who agree to our terms and conditions through the Synapse website. Test data will be kept hidden from participants. LISA data will be available at the time of the challenge and beyond to increase its usability and impact.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Organizers' evaluation software, metrics and ranking code used for the challenge will be available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial> and linked to our website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants must submit their containerized algorithm during the testing phase. Specific instructions for submission will be provided after challenge approval and will be detailed on the challenge website (Synapse). Participant containers will be made available for public use following the final testing/ranking phase of the challenge. Source code will be made available only at code authors' request.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge was funded by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation Grant INV-047887 as part of the UNITY Consortium.

All challenge organizers and data contributors will have access to the validation and test case labels.

We are also exploring Hyperfine as a potential sponsor for this challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance

- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Education, Research, Intervention follow up, Assistance, Intervention planning, Training, Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Recognition

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be all pediatric low field brain MRI.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort dataset will be healthy neonatal subjects approximately equal numbers of males and females scanned from the local population at :

- (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa
- (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital at Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda,
- (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Low field (0.064T) T2 MR images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For Task 1, challengers will be given ratings of the usability of the data in the form of number ratings across 7 artifact categories.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information about the subject will be available.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Imaging data will consist of the pediatric brain and skull shown in low resolution magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) T2 data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target will be low field T2 brain MR images.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Rate overall quality of low field MR images across 7 possible artifacts - motion, contrast, noise, zipper, positioning, banding and distortion with an error that reflects the intra-rater variability of an expert rater.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

For each data site, all low field images were obtained by scanning on a Hyperfine SWOOP, a 0.064T MR Scanner designed for FDA-approved portable brain imaging. The system is small enough to be put in patients' rooms and can be powered by standard electrical outlets. An attached Apple iPad handles postprocessing, from which, clinically useful images may be obtained.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Low field images from Hyperfine SWOOP at all three sites

Magnetic field strength 0.064T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 1.5s, TE 5ms, TI 400ms

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data was acquired at (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa, (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda, and. (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images were collected by trained personnel with experience imaging patients at the institutions listed above. All quality assurance evaluations were performed by an expert medical image evaluator.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case encompasses a trio of orthogonally acquired low field T2 MR images and ratings in each of the 7 artifact classes.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

For Task 1 (QA), we will provide 241 subjects of which 167, 37, and 37 subjects will be considered for training, validation, and testing, respectively.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases has been determined based on the available data. We collected data from different sites to introduce diversity, thereby avoiding overfitting and achieving better generalizability for the proposed models in the tasks. To prevent overlap between scans from one subject in the training cohort and those in the validation and test cohorts (due to multiple scans from a single subject), we will consider subjects rather than individual scans during the data division for training and validation. We follow the standard division of data for training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) and apply it to each site to get the final division for training, validation and test cohorts.

The number of subjects in training, validation and test cohorts is as follows. Each subject has three orthogonally acquired images (axial, sagittal, and coronal) - each with their own set of labels.

UCT, Uganda and AKU with 71, 48, and 48 training subjects from each site for a total of 167 subjects across 501 images with labels.

UCT, Uganda and AKU with 18, 6, and 13 validation subjects respectively for a total of 37 subjects across 111 images.

UCT, Uganda and AKU with 18, 6, and 13 test subjects respectively for a total of 37 subjects across 111 images.

Further images will be added to the training, validation and test image pool in order to increase the availability of data with 1 and 2 ratings across the 7 artifact domains.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

N/A

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

A single expert medical image evaluator was used to assess the quality of the data through manual image examination. A neuroradiologist reviewed and approved the assessment protocol.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The quality assessment protocol was based on the architecture found in [1], in order to rate motion, contrast, and noise. For the purpose of assessing the low field images, we also added categories for zipper, positioning banding,

and distortion artifacts with the definitions below.

Zipper

0: no zipper

1: Zipper is visible around the brain and interferes with brain contrast

2: Zipper is visible and causes severe distortion with brain contrast

Positioning / Complete FOV

0: Skull and cortex are within FOV

1: Any portion of the skull is missing from FOV

2: Both skull and any portion of the cortex have been cut from FOV

Banding

0: No Banding

1: Banding across the MR image where tissue contrast is still visible

2: Severe banding where tissue contrast is no longer visible

Distortion

0: No distortion of the brain

1: Any slight distortion of the brain which interferes lightly with brain contrast

2: Any distortion of the brain which severely affects the contrast between structures

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The rater has 10 years of experience in assessing MR image quality.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

n/a

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images were first converted to NIFTI from DICOM using dcm2nii. These low field images are defaced for full anonymization using our defacing pipeline which is available in our github repository located here -

<https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial/2025Preprocessing/tree/main>

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We will provide intra-rater reliability scores to estimate the magnitude of human error in image annotation.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

n/a

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will employ five distinct metrics including accuracy, F1 score, F2 score, precision, and recall.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Metric choices were based on recommendations found in [4], ensuring magnetic resonance imaging samples meet minimum quality requirements and contain no significant image artifacts.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We will take the mean across their respective metrics to obtain rankings. Standard deviations will also be calculated and given.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions that have missing results or cannot provide results because inference fails on a test case will be assigned the lowest possible score for the failed test case using metrics relevant to the task. For example, if a missing result or failed inference occurs in Task 1, the values for accuracy, F1 score, F2 score, precision, and recall would all be set to 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking system described will be used to obtain a fair and complete comparison across all metrics between participants. We desire a ranking scheme that is empirical, objective, and provides both participants and organizers with a clear understanding of the 'best' challenge solution.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Permutational analysis will be employed to evaluate uncertainties in rankings. Each team's QA performance will be assessed for all 7 artifact classes, considering each metric. Rankings for the measures will be combined by averaging, and statistical significance will be assessed exclusively for QA performance measures. This assessment will involve permuting the relative ranks for each QA measure, considering each artifact class for QA per subject in the testing data. Additionally, to obtain deeper insights into performance differences among multiple models from participants, we will apply Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. This will further enhance the statistical rigor of our analysis by providing pairwise comparisons of model performance, complementing the permutational approach and ensuring a more robust evaluation of statistical significance.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This permutation testing would reflect differences in performance that exceeded those that might be expected by chance.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

n/a

TASK 2: Segmentation of subcortical structures from low field neonatal MR images

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

During the initial stages of life, the human brain undergoes rapid tissue growth and development after birth. Accurately capturing and describing structural changes from magnetic resonance images (MRI) during this vital period is crucial for gaining new perspectives on healthy brain development and enabling the early identification of neurodevelopmental disorders.

While validated brain segmentation tools exist for adult brains, efforts to directly translate existing adult brain algorithms to pediatric MRI have generally failed. This is partly due to the poor gray/white matter differentiation of the developing brain and its rapid growth throughout the first years of life. These challenges impair the ability of existing algorithms to accurately segment pediatric brain structures even with high field (1.5T or 3T) MRI systems.

In low and middle-income countries, high field MRI systems are rare, due to the cost and maintenance required. More accessible MRI systems like the 0.064T Hyperfine scanner would help to assess gross anatomical abnormalities; structural delineation challenges are further compounded in these lower resolution imaging environments. Despite the loss in image quality and challenges with image analysis, there are great advantages of using low field MRI, including portability at the point of care of patients, small clinical costs with usability in low resource settings, and elimination of sedation for young children.

To drive advancements in automatic segmentation methods for low-field MRI, the LISA challenge introduces the second task. Participants are tasked with developing and evaluating deep learning methods for the automatic segmentation of subcortical structures such as the hippocampi and the basal ganglia in ultra low field (0.064T) T2-weighted magnetic resonance images of the healthy brain in early childhood.

The second task is centered around the automatic segmentation of subcortical structures such as the hippocampi which are pivotal subcortical structures linked to cognitive and memory functions, and often implicated in abnormal neurodevelopment and the basal ganglia, a group of subcortical nuclei critical for motor control, cognitive functions, and behavioral regulation, which are often implicated in disorders involving motor and executive dysfunction.

The LISA challenge provides challenge participants with the first-ever publicly available low-field MRI dataset, ensuring that the training, validation, and testing phases utilize the same dataset obtained from the Synapse platform. The overarching goal of the entire challenge is obtaining optimal deep learning tools for the assessment and segmentation of low-field MRI images in early childhood.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

pediatric, MRI, low field, segmentation, subcortical, hippocampus, basal ganglia, MICCAI, brain, neurodevelopment, Africa, South Asia

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Lead Organizers: Natasha Lepore (1,4) , Marius George Linguraru (2,3), Sean Deoni(6,7). Other organizers: Jeffrey Tanedo(1), Rahimeh Rouhi(1), Austin Tapp(2), Marvin Nelson(5). Data Contributors : Victoria Nankabirwa(8)(9), Sean Deoni (6,7), Kirsty Donald (10), Sadia Parkar (11), Sidra Kaleem (11), Salman Osmani (11)

1 CIBORG Laboratory, Department of Radiology, Children's Hospital Los Angeles; 2 Sheikh Zayed Institute for Pediatric Surgical Innovation, Children's National Hospital; 3 Departments of Radiology and Pediatrics, George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences; 4 Department of Pediatrics and Biomedical Engineering, University of Southern California; 6 Advanced Baby Imaging Lab, Rhode Island Hospital; 7 Departments of Pediatrics and Diagnostic Radiology, Warren Alpert Medical School at Brown University; 8 Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda; 9 St. Francis Hospital - Nsambya, Kampala, Uganda ; 10 Department of Paediatrics and Child Health, University of Cape Town; 11 Aga Khan University Hospital

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Natasha Lepore - nlepore@chla.usc.edu
 Children's Hospital Los Angeles
 4650 Sunset Blvd, Los Angeles, CA, 90027, USA
 Department of Radiology and Imaging
 Phone: 323-361-2411

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

As with the LISA 2024 Challenge, we plan to use the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks; Synapse.org) for the challenge. This platform has been used for numerous other challenges, including the CBTN-CONNECT-DIPGr-ASNR-MICCAI Pediatric Brain Tumor Segmentation Challenge 2023, organized by Dr. Linguraru.

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

synapse.org Synapse Project SynID is syn53282349. <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn55249552/wiki/626951>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Data used to train algorithms is not restricted to only the data provided by the challenge. Publicly available online and/or synthetic datasets are allowed. Our aim is to solve the segmentation and quality assurance of low-field MRI with the best possible tools. Investigator -owned data may be used only if data is made available to the community before August 8th, 2025, which is when the testing phase begins.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

As this segmentation task will be divided into two subtasks for two subcortical structures, the bilateral hippocampi and bilateral basal ganglia, prizes for this task will also be divided. Challengers are allowed to participate in both subtasks and would be eligible to win in both subtasks separately.

First prize in each subtask will be awarded \$500 each.

Second prize in each subtask will be awarded \$250 each.

Third prize in each subtask will be awarded \$125 each.

Top three teams in each subtask will receive award certificates.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods for each subtask will be announced publicly and these participants will be invited to present their method. All participant rankings (training, validation and testing) will also be made publicly available on the challenge website leaderboard. All participant methods that are ranked in the testing phase will have their accompanying short LNCS style paper (see section f) made visible to organizers and challenge participants. Making the participants' paper public will support methodological reproducibility and the open-source spirit the organizers seek to embody in this challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Authors participating in the evaluation of their containerized model against the unseen test data are required to submit a short 8- to 11- page LNCS style paper through the LISA CMT by Friday, July 25th at 11:59 PM Pacific Time. Papers will be reviewed for suitability for online distribution. If challenge organizers deem that the method is not reproducible via the short paper instructions, then the method will not be evaluated and thus not considered for ranking. In some cases, organizers may provide comments to improve the short paper within the deadline. Details on training time and resources required to reproduce a participant's submission will be required in the short paper. Challenge participants must abide by the guiding principles for responsible research use and data handling within the Synapse Commons Platform as described in the Synapse Governance documents and by the Challenge's Official Rules. Publication embargo: Challenge participants are permitted to publish individual challenge results restricted to their own submitted method and ranking. Overall Challenge results or analysis thereof is restricted until Challenge organizers and participants have jointly published (or pre-published) an overview paper on the results and best performing strategies. The challenge organizers intend to aggregate the methods and summarize the results of LISA 2025 as a single journal manuscript with the goal of publication in journals of Medical Image Analysis, IEEE TMI, or a journal of similar impact factor. Participants will be contacted through Synapse-affiliated email addresses when this condition has been met. This information will also be posted within this Synapse project. Acknowledgement: Challenge participants and other data users are permitted to use, publish and present the Challenge results, after the embargo period, provided they acknowledge the LISA challenge organizing members as follows: "Data used in this publication were obtained as part of MICCAI 2025's Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance (LISA) Challenge through Synapse ID syn53282349", Publications using challenge resources will be required to cite the overview paper of LISA 2025 and acknowledge the support of the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, which provided funding used for supporting data collection, curation, and processing.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Validation and Training Phase segmentation prediction files are to be submitted on the Synapse Platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn55249552/wiki/627686>

Test Phase submissions are done via MLCube containers submitted on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn55249552/wiki/627696>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

To permit participant's method fine tuning, we will release the validation set in June (see timetable below). Validation ground truth data will not be released, but scores based on predictions will be provided to participants. Participants can select their final test submissions based on these validation results. After the validation phase ends, participants are allowed a maximum of 2 final testing submissions for each task, or 4 total submissions. The best scoring method of each task (2 methods per team) will be selected for final ranking. Neither test images nor their ground truths will be made public.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Wednesday, 16 April 2025

Challenge launch

Registration opens

Wednesday, 30 April 2025

Release of training data with ground truth labels

Tuesday, 17 June 2025

Release of validation data (without labels)

Tuesday, 24 June 2025

Validation phase opens

Friday, 25 July 2025

Validation phase ends (submission deadline of segmentation files)

Submission deadline of short papers in CMT, reporting method and preliminary results.

Saturday, 26 July 2025

Testing phase opens

(available only to participants who submitted short papers)

Saturday, 9 August 2025

Testing phase ends (submission deadline of MLCubes)

Saturday, 9 August – Friday, 29 August 2025

Evaluation of MLCubes on testing data

(performed by challenge organizers)

Monday, 1 September 2025

Top performing methods contacted for preparing oral presentation slides

Tuesday–Saturday, 23–27 September 2025

Presentation of Challenge, Announcement of the final top 3 ranked teams

Late October 2025

Camera-ready submission of extended papers for inclusion in the associated workshop proceedings

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The low-high field magnetic resonance image data that will be used for the training, validation, and testing of algorithms was acquired through the UNITY project funded by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) at multiple international sites. Ethics approval was obtained at each site following the local standards and all data were fully de-identified before inclusion in the project. The protocol for releasing the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data contributing institution and data inclusion in the LISA challenge was approved by the BMGF. Training and validation data will be made available to challenge participants who agree to our terms and conditions through the Synapse website. Test data will be kept hidden from participants. LISA data will be available at the time of the challenge and beyond to increase its usability and impact.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Organizers' evaluation software, metrics and ranking code used for the challenge will be available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial> and linked to our website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants must submit their containerized algorithm during the testing phase. Specific instructions for submission will be provided after challenge approval and will be detailed on the challenge website (Synapse). Participant containers will be made available for public use following the final testing/ranking phase of the challenge. Source code will be made available only at code authors' request.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge was funded by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation Grant INV-047887 as part of the UNITY Consortium.

All challenge organizers and data contributors will have access to the validation and test case labels. We are also exploring Hyperfine as a potential sponsor for this challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Assistance,Diagnosis,Education,Intervention follow up,Intervention planning,Research,Screening,Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval

- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be all pediatric low field brain MRI.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort dataset will be healthy neonatal subjects approximately equal numbers of males and females scanned from the local population at :

- (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa
- (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital at Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda,
- (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Low field (0.064T) T2 MR images and ONLY segmentations derived from matching high field (3T or 1.5T) T2 MR images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For Task 2, challengers will have access to manually segmented subcortical structure data (bilateral hippocampi, ventricles, and basal ganglia) from matching high field data.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information about the subject will be available.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Imaging data will consist of the pediatric brain and skull shown in low resolution magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) T2 data. For Task 2, there will also be a set of manually corrected bilateral hippocampi, ventricles, and basal ganglia. Bilateral ventricles are offered to allow teams to use multi-label segmentation algorithms should they wish to do so. However, the use of the ventricles for either subtask is not required.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target will be MRI subcortical segmentations, including: Task 2A: the bilateral hippocampi; and Task 2B: bilateral basal ganglia. These structures will be annotated from high field images, and obtained from matching low field T2 brain MR images.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Find high field bilateral hippocampi segmentations for Task 2A and bilateral basal ganglia segmentations for Task 2B for pediatric low field MR T2 images. Metrics include Dice coefficient, Hausdorff distance, average symmetric surface distance, and relative volume error.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

For each data site, all low field images were obtained by scanning on a Hyperfine SWOOP, a 0.064T MR Scanner designed for FDA-approved portable brain imaging. The system is small enough to be put in patients' rooms and can be powered by standard electrical outlets. An attached Apple iPad handles postprocessing, from which, clinically useful images may be obtained.

For the high field images (1.5 or 3T MRI) which will be used for the ground truth subcortical segmentations, high field T2 scans were obtained at the University of Cape Town, Makerere University, and Aga Khan University Hospital on, respectively, a Siemens 3T Skyra, Siemens 1.5T Sempra, and Toshiba 3T Titan scanner within days of scanning on the Hyperfine SWOOP in order to obtain low and high field matching T2 image pairs.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Low field images from Hyperfine SWOOP used at both sites

Magnetic field strength 0.064T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 1.5s, TE 5ms, TI 400ms

High field images at Makerere University

Magnetic field strength 1.5T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 5s, TE 95 ms

High field images at AKU

Magnetic field strength 3T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 3.2s, TE 352 ms

High field images at UCT

Magnetic field strength 3T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 3.2s, TE 561 ms

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data was acquired at (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa, (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda, and. (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images were collected by trained personnel with experience imaging patients at the institutions listed above. All subcortical segmentations were approved by a board certified pediatric neuroradiologist.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case encompasses a preprocessed low field T2 MR image and a single accompanying high field MR segmentation of the bilateral hippocampi, ventricles, and basal ganglia with the following labels : 0 - background, 1- right hippocampus, 2 - left hippocampus, 3 - right lateral ventricle, 4 - left lateral ventricle, 5 - right basal ganglia, 6 - left basal ganglia.

All data will be made available for both subtasks, but Task 2A will focus on bilateral hippocampi output whereas Task 2B will focus on bilateral basal ganglia output. There will be no subtask for the bilateral ventricles as this data is meant to support both subtasks.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The images in validation and testing used in the QA task that also have matched high field data will be considered for validation and testing in the segmentation task. Additional data is being acquired through the UNITY Consortium and will be added as it becomes available. .

The number of subjects in training, validation and test cohorts is as follows.

UCT, Uganda, and AKU with 72, 16, and 12 training cases respectively for a total of 100 cases.

UCT, Uganda, and AKU with 11, 2, and 7 validation cases respectively for a total of 20 cases.

UCT, Uganda, and AKU with 11, 2, and 7 test cases respectively for a total of 20 cases.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases has been determined based on the available data. We collected data from different sites to introduce diversity, thereby avoiding overfitting and achieving better generalizability for the proposed models in the tasks. To prevent overlap between scans from one subject in the training cohort and those in the validation and test cohorts (due to multiple scans from a single subject), we will consider subjects rather than individual scans during the data division for training and validation. We follow the standard division of data for training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) and apply it to each site to get the final division for training, validation and test cohorts.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

N/A

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Initial segmentation/annotation was performed manually by research assistants, and were corrected manually by an expert rater in the high field image. A neuroradiologist reviewed and approved the segmentation protocol. To obtain ground truth data in the low-field MRI space, we linearly register low-field T2 images to their high-field T2 counterparts. These image pairs have less than 10% age differential between MRI scan times to ensure proper anatomical alignment. After quantitative and qualitative assurance checks for registration accuracy, we perform manual segmentations on the high-field images in shared low-field/high-field space, and manually correct any slight segmentation errors using visible anatomical boundaries gleaned in the low-field image. We will also release intra- and inter-rater reliability scores with the initial data release.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

An outline of the segmentation protocol is detailed below. A similar protocol is used for the bilateral ventricles and basal ganglia.

Hippocampus Segmentation Protocol in ITK-SNAP

1. Loading the Main Image:

Launch ITK-SNAP, and load the main MRI image containing the brain structure of interest.

2. Adjusting Image Contrast:

Navigate to the "Tools" menu.

Adjust Image contrast to optimize contrast settings for differentiating white matter and gray matter.

3. Defining Labels:

Label 1 (red): Represents the left hippocampus.

Label 2 (green): Represents the right hippocampus.

4. Main Toolbar:

Use the crosshair mode to select a voxel of interest, which will be displayed in all three planes. Adjust the zoom level as per your preference.

Utilize the paint brush mode for segmenting regions.

Using a Square Brush Shape (Size 2), maintain a consistent 2x2 voxel boundary for accurate segmentation.

6. Starting in Sagittal View:

Identify a sagittal slice that exhibits the maximum extent of the hippocampus.

Begin segmenting the gray matter while adjusting the brush opacity as needed.

Pay attention to the boundaries where the anterior and posterior sides of the hippocampus meet, especially at the ventricles.

7. Lateral Segmentation in Sagittal View:

Gradually move laterally (away from the brain center) and continue segmenting the hippocampus slice by slice.

Hippocampus will gradually become smaller and thinner.

8. Medial Segmentation in Sagittal View:

After reaching the lateral boundary, move medially (toward the brain center).

Identify the "claw-shaped" structure, which may represent the ventricles.

The "thumb" of this claw determines when to split the hippocampus in the sagittal view.

Ensure a gradual split of the hippocampus without abrupt shape shifts, maintaining the integrity of the structure.

9. Segmenting the Head and Tail:

After the split, continue segmentation until the anterior head of the hippocampus disappears. The posterior tail will gradually vanish after the head disappears.

10. Coronal View Segmentation:

Begin segmentation from the posterior side in the coronal view.

Progress slice by slice towards the anterior side, identifying contrast differences as well as consistency in the shape shifting.

Employ crosshair mode more frequently in the coronal view to validate segmentation from the sagittal view.

11. Axial View Segmentation:

Start segmentation from the superior side in the axial view.

Move slice by slice towards the inferior side.

As you approach the endpoint in the axial view, ensure that the segmentation concludes before the corpus callosum joins. This serves as your reference for the boundary in the axial view.

12. Maintaining 2x2 Voxel Density:

Throughout the segmentation process, prevent holes or any 1x1 voxel stranding.

Maintaining a 2x2 voxel density is crucial for accurate boundary preservation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Our neuroradiologist has a number of decades of experience in assessing hippocampi segmentations.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

n/a

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images were first converted to NIFTI from DICOM using dcm2nii. These low field images are defaced for full anonymization using our defacing pipeline which is available in our github repository located here - <https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial/2025Preprocessing/tree/main>

Each orthogonally acquired trio of anisotropic low field T2 images are reconstructed to form a single higher resolution combined isotropic T2 image as described in [2].

These images and all background high resolution images then follow a processing pipeline of bias field correction, skullstripping and linear registration as detailed in [3].

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We will provide intra-rater reliability scores to estimate the magnitude of human error in image annotation.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

n/a

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will employ four metrics, Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff Distance (HD), Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), and Relative Volume Error (RVE) on the respective segmentation predictions for both subtasks.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Metric choice was chosen from recommendations found in [5] which presents a checklist which authors of biomedical image analysis challenges are encouraged to include in their submission when giving a paper on a challenge into review. The purpose of the checklist is to standardize and facilitate the review process and raise interpretability and reproducibility of challenge results by making relevant information explicit.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

For each subtask, we will take the mean across their respective metrics in order obtain rankings. Standard deviations will also be calculated and given.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions that have missing results or cannot provide results because inference fails on a test case will be assigned the lowest possible score for the failed test case using metrics relevant to the task. For example, if a missing result or failed inference occurs in Task 2, values would be set to 0% for DSC, the maximum size of the image for both HD and ASSD, and 100% for relative volume error.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking system described will be used to obtain a fair and complete comparison across all metrics between participants. We desire a ranking scheme that is empirical, objective, and provides both participants and organizers with a clear understanding of the 'best' challenge solution.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Permutational analyses will be employed to evaluate uncertainties in rankings. Separately, in each subtask, each team's performance will be evaluated separately for the left and right subcortical structures. Rankings for the measures will be combined by averaging, and statistical significance will be assessed exclusively for segmentation performance measures. This assessment will involve permuting the relative ranks for each segmentation measure, considering left and right subcortical structure segmentation, per subject in the testing data.

Additionally, to obtain deeper insights into performance differences among multiple models from participants, we will apply Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. This will further enhance the statistical rigor of our analysis by providing pairwise comparisons of model performance, complementing the permutational approach and ensuring a more robust evaluation of statistical significance.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

This permutation testing would reflect differences in performance that exceeded those that might be expected by chance

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,

- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

n/a

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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- [3] Rouhi, R., Tanedo, J., Wei, I.M., Valder, M., Zanjali, S., Gajawelli, N., ... & Lepore, N. (2023, November). Automated Segmentation of the Hippocampus in Pediatric Imaging. In 2023 19th International Symposium on Medical Information Processing and Analysis (SIPAIM) (pp. 1-5), IEEE.
- [4] Ravi D; Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative; Barkhof F, Alexander DC, Puglisi L, Parker GJM, Eshaghi A. An efficient semi-supervised quality control system trained using physics-based MRI-artefact generators and adversarial training. *Med Image Anal.* 2024 Jan;91:103033. doi 10.1016/j.media.2023.103033 Epub 2023 Nov 20. PMID 38000256
- [5] Lena Maier-Hein, Annika Reinke, Michal Kozubek, Anne L. Martel, Tal Arbel, Matthias Eisenmann, Allan Hanbury, Pierre Jannin, Henning Müller, Sinan Onogur, Julio Saez-Rodriguez, Bram van Ginneken, Annette Kopp-Schneider, Bennett A. Landman, BIAS: Transparent reporting of biomedical image analysis challenges, *Medical Image Analysis*, Volume 66, 2020, 101796, ISSN 1361-8415, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2020.101796>.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

n/a